

JALON

Regional Energy Community Project Design
[Alentejo Central / Portugal]

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1. Context

This project is developed within the scope of the JALON project (Grant Agreement No. 101076395), funded under the LIFE Clean Energy Transition programme of the European Union, which seeks to accelerate the establishment of regional renewable energy communities (RECs) through participatory, scalable, and territorially adapted models. The central pillar of JALON is the implementation of a large-scale REC in the Comunidad de Calatayud (Spain), coordinated by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), and co-created by local citizens, municipalities, and project partners.

A key component of JALON's design is the intentional replication of this experience in other European territories with comparable challenges. As defined in Task T5.3, the regions of Alentejo Central (Portugal) and South Tyrol (Italy) were selected to develop their own REC designs, informed by direct observation of the Calatayud pilot and enriched by regional specificities. During the implementation of the JALON project, the partners Universidade de Évora (UEVORA), CIMAC (Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alentejo Central), and EURAC have actively followed the participatory processes, technical planning, and governance structure of the Calatayud REC, attending workshops, stakeholder meetings, and internal consortium exchanges.

Through this immersion, the Portuguese replication team has been able to critically assess the conditions necessary to adapt the JALON methodology to the territorial, social, and institutional reality of Alentejo Central. This region presents a unique opportunity to demonstrate how a large-scale, bottom-up energy community can contribute simultaneously to the energy transition, the revitalization of rural areas, and the strengthening of local governance and citizen engagement.

This document represents the first formal outcome of the replication effort in Alentejo Central. It lays out a conceptual and technical framework for the creation of a regional REC that is consistent with the core principles of JALON: citizen-led design, institutional cooperation, social innovation, and climate resilience. The aim is not only to design an implementable community energy project for the region, but also to produce a replicable model for rural Europe, reinforcing the role of RECs as instruments of systemic transformation.

2. Scope of the project design

2.1 Background

The Alentejo Central sub-region stands at a crossroads of structural fragility and latent potential, a duality that underscores the importance and relevance of implementing a Regional Renewable Energy Community (REC) in the territory. Spanning approximately 7,393.5 km² and home to around 153,475 inhabitants, the region exhibits a very low population density (≈ 20.8 inhabitants/km²), reflecting long-standing patterns of rural dispersion and limited territorial occupation^{1,2}.

Figure 1: Map of Portugal and sub-regions of Alentejo (source <http://web2.spi.pt/alentejo/>)

Demographically, Alentejo Central confronts pronounced ageing trends and population decline. Over the past decade, the sub-region has registered a sustained decrease in resident population, with negative natural and migratory balance and an increase in the elderly population

¹ "PORDATA - Estatísticas, gráficos e indicadores." Accessed: Apr. 15, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pordata.pt/home>

² "Anuários Estatísticos Regionais" Accessed: Apr. 15, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_doc_municipios

percentage^{3,4,5}. This demographic shift has cascading effects on economic dynamism, labour availability, social structure, and the viability of public services, especially in smaller towns and rural parishes where depopulation and ageing are more acute³.

These demographic trends combine with socio-economic vulnerabilities. The region historically suffers from low population retention, particularly of youth and skilled labour, translating into limited opportunities for innovation, entrepreneurship, and long-term economic growth⁶. The decline in population is accompanied by a deterioration in the availability and quality of basic services, including access to energy, mobility, and institutional infrastructures, features that exacerbate social exclusion, isolation, and energy vulnerability in dispersed rural communities⁷.

Furthermore, like many rural territories, Alentejo Central is particularly exposed to the risks of energy poverty and social exclusion, especially among elderly residents, low-income households, and remote communities with limited access to efficient and affordable energy services⁸.

At the same time, Alentejo Central holds considerable natural and structural assets that favour a transition to renewable energy: extensive land availability, abundant solar irradiation, and an already significant, but still underexploited, photovoltaic (PV) infrastructure. Indeed, the sub-region benefits from a comparatively high potential for renewable energy generation⁶.

Institutionally, the presence of CIMAC (Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alentejo Central), coordinating 14 municipalities, provides a robust governance framework for intermunicipal cooperation and collective planning³. In addition, the region's cultural and natural heritage, coupled with emerging opportunities in sustainable tourism and agriculture, represent alternative economic development pathways that can be synergistically reinforced by a community-scale renewable energy strategy⁶.

This context, marked by demographic decline, social vulnerability, energy and service fragility on one hand, and by renewable resource abundance, institutional capacity, and territorial assets on the other, creates a compelling case for the design of a regional energy community. Such an initiative could address multiple structural challenges at once: providing cleaner and more affordable energy; revitalizing local economies; supporting social inclusion; and offering a replicable blueprint of community-led energy governance for rural Europe.

In light of these considerations, the present proposal seeks to leverage the methodological framework developed under the JALON project by transplanting and adapting it to the specific conditions of Alentejo Central. The REC is envisioned not just as an energy infrastructure plan, but as a strategic instrument of territorial regeneration, social cohesion, and climate-resilient development.

³ "Demografia". Accessed: Dec. 11,2025. [Online]. Available: www.cimac.pt/visitante/alentejo-central/caracterizacao/demografia/

⁴ CIMAC (2021). Avaliação e atualização da estratégia integrada de desenvolvimento territorial do alentejo central para o período de programação 2021-2027.

⁵ CME (2023). Demografia e caracterização social.

⁶ OECD (2025). Rethinking Regional Attractiveness in the Portuguese region of Alentejo.

⁷ European Commission (2008). Poverty and social exclusion in rural areas.

⁸ OECD (2022). Delivering Quality Services to All in Alentejo: Preparing Regions for Demographic Change.

2.2 Objective

The main objective of this project is to develop a technically viable, socially inclusive, and territorially integrated design for a regional energy community in Alentejo Central. The proposed REC will aim to:

- Accelerate the decarbonisation of the local energy system through distributed solar energy;
- Promote the democratisation of energy production and governance, placing citizens and public institutions at the center of decision-making;
- Reduce energy poverty and social inequalities by offering more affordable and participatory energy solutions;
- Strengthen rural resilience, helping to counteract depopulation and economic marginalisation;
- Serve as a replicable model for other low-density rural territories in Portugal and across Europe.

More than a technical intervention, this project positions RECs as a catalyst for territorial transformation and social innovation, contributing to European and national climate goals while fostering new forms of local cooperation, empowerment, and solidarity.

2.3 Concept and methodology

The implementation of a REC in Alentejo Central is conceived as a three-phase process, following the strategic and operational logic developed in the JALON project. The goal is to establish a regionally coordinated, citizen-led REC that is scalable, inclusive, and adapted to the rural realities of the territory.

Phase 1 – Seeding and Mobilisation (Years 0–1)

The first phase focuses on the legal constitution of the REC, the engagement of key stakeholders, and the creation of a participatory framework across the region. This involves:

- Forming a core promotional group, led by CIMAC and UEVORA, to define the legal structure, governance model, and strategic vision for the REC;
- Involving municipalities, especially elected officials and technical staff, to build trust, secure access to public infrastructures, and ensure territorial alignment;
- Conducting public engagement campaigns through participatory events in target municipalities (e.g., assemblies, workshops, co-design labs), aimed at reaching at least 13.5% of the population in each area, following the innovation diffusion theory used in JALON;
- Deploying a professional field team, composed of paid staff with expertise in social facilitation, renewable energy, and local development. This team will coordinate awareness-raising, training, and community support efforts;
- Engaging local installers and technicians to ensure local capacity building and alignment with the regional labour market.

Phase 2 – Project Design and Development (Years 1–3)

Overlapping with Phase 1, this stage involves the technical and financial development of PV projects that reflect the participatory priorities and local capacities identified earlier. Key actions include:

- The technical dimensioning of distributed PV systems, based on energy consumption data, solar potential, and the location of public and private assets;
- Defining the number, location, and capacity of systems needed to meet the energy targets of the REC;
- Drafting and validating the business plan for the REC, including CAPEX/OPEX models, shared cost structures, energy-sharing contracts, and risk mitigation strategies;
- Ensuring economic viability by combining investment and public funding;
- Using and adapting the JALON tools and templates (technical specifications, contracts, statutes, methodologies) to the Portuguese legal and regulatory framework.

Phase 3 – Operation and Expansion

Once the initial projects are ready for implementation, the REC will move to the operation phase, focusing on:

- Managing shared self-consumption and energy flows across the REC to maximise local impact and reduce energy costs;
- Establishing an operational governance structure for the community and ensuring ongoing transparency, accountability, and adaptability;
- Promoting additional projects in storage, mobility, and energy efficiency, based on community demand and regional opportunities;
- Ensuring long-term sustainability through continuous training, reinvestment mechanisms, and territorial monitoring.

The regional scale of the REC is essential to its systemic impact. Unlike isolated local energy communities, a regional REC allows for:

- Aggregation of supply and demand, improving technical efficiency and economic returns;
- Solidarity-based redistribution of energy and benefits across municipalities;
- Visibility and legitimacy, essential for political and institutional support at regional and national levels.

This scale, however, requires a professionalised field presence in the territory throughout all phases, which entails upfront coordination costs. Therefore, the business plan will define not only the energy and financial targets of the REC, but also the annual resource needs (personnel, vehicles, communications) required to meet those targets.

The Alentejo Central REC thus emerges as a structured, phased, and place-based response to the challenges of the energy transition in rural territories. By combining JALON methodology with local realities, it aims to become a model of regional cooperation, citizen empowerment, and climate-resilient development.

2.4 Scope of the Project

This document outlines the proposed Renewable Energy Community (REC) project design for Alentejo Central (Portugal). The design addresses the REC implementation pathway defined in the Concept and Methodology section, and it is based on the criteria and principles established by the JALON project, namely the development of a regional-scale REC built through a bottom-up approach and strong collaboration between citizens and local/regional authorities.

The JALON principles establish that: (i) a regional REC should aim to reach all towns within the target territory over time; (ii) the REC should be implemented bottom-up by citizens, supported by municipalities and the relevant regional/intermunicipal public body; and (iii) the REC should pursue objectives that go beyond energy generation alone, namely to combat rural depopulation, promote territorial cohesion, provide affordable and locally available renewable energy, and promote renewable energy and energy efficiency actions adapted to local needs. In operational terms, the REC may also require the capability to act in the electricity market (including management of surpluses and market representation), subject to compliance with the applicable Portuguese legal and regulatory framework.

Accordingly, the scope of the Alentejo Central regional REC project design is defined by the following points:

Legal Aspects:

- Establishing the activities of the REC and determining their compliance with current legislation.

Organisational Aspects:

- Definition of the REC legal form.
- Definition of the local team.
- Identification and characterization of the target population.
- Methodology to raise awareness among the population.

Technical Aspects

- Characterization of electricity consumption.
- Criteria to size the PV self-consumption systems.
- Design of the PV self-consumption systems.

Financial Aspects

- Definition of a business plan.
- Definition of the financing scheme.

In sum, the scope of this pre-operational design is to deliver a complete and actionable blueprint for the implementation of a regional-scale REC in Alentejo Central, grounded in real data, participatory methods, legal viability, and long-term financial coherence.

3. Characterization of the region

3.1 Description of the target region

The proposed Renewable Energy Community (REC) will be implemented in Alentejo Central, corresponding to the district of Évora in southern Portugal. To characterise the region, demographic and socio-economic indicators referring mainly to 2023 were compiled from PORDATA and the Regional Statistical Yearbooks^{1,2}.

Alentejo Central is a predominantly rural territory, covering 7,393.5 km² and hosting 153,475 residents, which results in a population density of 20.76 inhabitants/km². This places the region among the most sparsely populated areas in Portugal. Such territorial characteristics constrain access to services, reinforce socio-economic asymmetries, and make purely centralised energy solutions less effective, thereby supporting the strategic rationale for a regional and decentralised REC.

Administratively, the region comprises 14 municipalities, with Évora as the main urban centre and administrative hub. Most other municipalities are characterised by small villages and dispersed settlements, facing different degrees of depopulation, territorial isolation, and underinvestment. These structural challenges are amplified by a marked ageing trend: 27.1% of residents are aged 65+, while only 15.9% are under 15. The working-age population represents about 57% of the total, implying a dependency structure that increases pressure on local public services and economic activity.

Educational attainment among the active population suggests a persistent skills gap: 39.9% have completed only basic education (up to 9th grade), while 25.2% hold a higher education degree. Income levels are modest, with an average gross monthly income of €1,167.20, and a notable gender gap (€1,250.93 for men versus €1,070.93 for women). Additionally, 3,552 residents are beneficiaries of the national Social Insertion Income (RSI), indicating the presence of poverty and energy vulnerability pockets that are relevant for the REC's social objectives.

Despite these vulnerabilities, Alentejo Central has meaningful institutional and infrastructural capacity to support the deployment of a regional REC. The region is coordinated by CIMAC (Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alentejo Central), which provides an established structure for intermunicipal cooperation and strategic planning. The presence of the University of Évora further strengthens local capacity through renewable energy research, technical expertise, and stakeholder engagement. The territory also hosts a diversified base of activity and public infrastructure, including 21,436 companies, 169 schools, 6 higher education establishments, 88 pharmacies, and 197 registered tourist accommodations, contributing to seasonal and sectoral diversity in electricity demand.

Figure 2: Map of Alentejo Central and its municipalities (source www.heraldicacivica.pt/).

3.2 Characterization of electricity consumption in the region

Electricity consumption in Alentejo Central reflects both the dispersed settlement pattern of the region and the relevance of residential demand in small and medium-sized municipalities. Using data from national electricity distribution statistics and municipal population census figures for 2023^{1,2}, residential electricity consumption was characterised at municipal level, allowing for a consistent comparison across territories with different population sizes and consumer bases.

In 2023, total electricity consumption in Alentejo Central, including all sectors, was 832,249,590 kWh distributed across the following categories:

- Residential consumption: 250,004,732 kWh
- Non-residential (commercial, public services, etc.): 180,628,981 kWh
- Industrial consumption: 301,520,667 kWh
- Agricultural consumption: 63,113,061 kWh
- Public lighting: 7,118,861 kWh
- State building lighting: 29,863,288 kWh

These values highlight the significant energy requirements of the region, not only from households but also from productive sectors such as agriculture and industry. Any Regional Energy Community must therefore address both residential needs and opportunities for shared self-consumption across sectors and actors.

To support technical planning, Table 1 provides a detailed view of residential electricity consumption, installed PV capacity, and estimated PV production for each municipality. Residential electricity consumption per consumer varies moderately across the 14 municipalities of Alentejo Central. Higher consumption is observed in municipalities such as Évora, Montemor-

o-Novo and Borba while lower values are recorded in Mora, Mourão and Estremoz reflecting differences in household composition, building efficiency, and local socio-economic conditions.

Table 1: Residential electricity consumption, installed PV capacity, and estimated PV production per residential consumer in each municipality of Alentejo Central.

Municipality	2023 Number of residential consumers	2023 Residential consumption (kWh/residential consumer)	2024 Installed PV Capacity (kWp)	2024 Estimated PV Production (kWh/residential consumer)
Alandroal	3606	2548.51	1112.98	497.85
Arraiolos	4262	2830.69	2308.94	873.84
Borba	3652	2922.82	2164.04	955.80
Estremoz	7756	2533.16	3578.21	744.15
Évora	28326	3055.62	12345.99	703.03
Montemor-o-Novo	9060	2856.55	4493.38	799.98
Mora	3221	2136.45	810.68	405.97
Mourão	1685	2435.36	846.47	810.30
Portel	3797	2555.76	1381.86	587.03
Redondo	3959	2600.77	1337.64	544.99
Reguengos de Monsaraz	6272	2763.69	3902.79	1003.70
Vendas Novas	6205	2720.42	4103.55	1066.72
Viana do Alentejo	3312	2737.63	1889.75	920.34
Vila Viçosa	4283	2738.40	743.33	279.94
Alentejo Central	89396	2796.60	41019.61	740.13

In parallel, photovoltaic deployment at municipal level was analysed using data from the E-REDES Open Data Portal⁹, which provides information on the number of PV installations and total installed capacity per municipality. However, as E-REDES does not provide direct information on annual energy production, PV electricity generation was estimated using the PVGIS tool¹⁰. The 2024 installed PV capacity in the region totals 41,019.61 kWp, distributed unevenly between municipalities. Estimated annual production per residential consumer was calculated under typical conditions, with the value for the Alentejo Central region being 740.13 kWh/consumer. This suggests that, if the installed PV were for residential consumption only, on average, only about a quarter of residential demand would be covered by local PV generation, with some municipalities like Vendas Novas, Borba and Reguengos de Monsaraz exceeding 900 kWh/consumer while others such as Vila Viçosa and Mora remain significantly underpowered.

⁹ E-REDES. "Total de unidades de produção para autoconsumo." Accessed: Apr. 15, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/8-unidades-de-producao-para-autoconsumo/table/>

¹⁰ Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS). Accessed on Jan. 29, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/

This variability reflects differences in existing installed capacity and deployment patterns rather than solar resource availability alone.

Overall, the comparison between residential electricity consumption and estimated PV production highlights a substantial gap between current local generation and demand in most municipalities. In all cases, estimated PV production covers only a fraction of residential electricity consumption, reinforcing the opportunity and need for expanding distributed photovoltaic generation through a coordinated regional Renewable Energy Community.

The availability of harmonised, municipality-level consumption and generation indicators provides a robust basis for:

- defining priority municipalities for initial REC deployment;
- identifying territories with higher potential for shared self-consumption schemes;
- supporting equitable energy-sharing mechanisms across municipalities with different demographic and infrastructural characteristics.

This territorial and quantitative diagnosis confirms that a regional-scale REC is particularly suited to Alentejo Central, enabling aggregation of production and demand across municipalities and allowing smaller or less-equipped territories to benefit from collective renewable energy solutions.

3.3 Identification of key stakeholders

The development and long-term success of a Regional Energy Community (REC) in Alentejo Central depends on the active involvement of a diverse and complementary group of stakeholders. These actors will play critical roles in the design, implementation, governance, and expansion of the REC, ensuring its technical, financial, social, and institutional viability.

Energy Communities stakeholders

- CIMAC – Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alentejo Central (<https://www.cimac.pt/>): CIMAC is a key institutional stakeholder coordinating intermunicipal cooperation across the 14 municipalities of Alentejo Central. It plays a central role in the integrated territorial development strategy of the region and is a natural promoter of regional-scale energy communities. Within the scope of this REC design, CIMAC will coordinate with municipalities to facilitate access to public infrastructure, support regulatory compliance, and ensure institutional articulation with regional and national programmes.
- University of Évora (UEVORA, <https://www.uevora.pt/>): UEVORA, through its Renewable Energies Chair and various EU-funded projects (e.g. JALON, AURORA, PRR-AATE), contributes technical-scientific support for the energy transition in rural territories. UEVORA will act as a technical advisor to the REC initiative, providing expertise in photovoltaic system design, regional energy modelling, participatory methodologies, and impact evaluation.

- ADENE – Agência para a Energia (<https://www.adene.pt/>): ADENE is the national energy agency of Portugal and supports the development of energy communities through capacity-building, regulatory interpretation, and technical resources.
- AREANATEjo - Agência Regional de Energia e Ambiente do Norte Alentejano e Tejo (<https://www.areanatejo.pt/>): AREANATEjo is a Energy and Environment Agency of the North Alentejo region that also has activity in the Alentejo Central sub-region, in particular in Évora, due to the lack of presence of a regional agency. It supports the development of energy communities with technical resources, capacity-building and regulatory interpretation.

Social stakeholders

- IPSS and “Misericórdias” across the municipalities (Évora: <https://scmevora.pt/>): Local social solidarity institutions can support outreach and recruitment, identify vulnerable households through existing support networks, and potentially participate as REC members through their facilities (social buildings with relevant loads). Other IPSS entities present in the region include Red Cross and Cáritas delegations.
- EAPN Portugal (<https://www.eapn.pt/>): Network working on poverty and social inclusion can contribute with framing, indicators, and good practices for monitoring social outcomes (affordability, inclusion, and energy poverty mitigation), which is especially relevant for reporting and impact evaluation.
- Consumer organisations (<https://www.deco.proteste.pt/>): Consumer advocacy organisations are relevant to support clear communication on bills, rights, and savings mechanisms, increasing transparency and trust, particularly important in early phases when detailed consumption profiles are not yet available.
- Local development associations: Development associations with a strong field presence can support community mobilisation, workshops, and local engagement in smaller villages where municipal technical capacity may be limited and informal trust networks are decisive.

Technical stakeholders

- E-REDES – Distribution System Operator (DSO, <https://www.e-redes.pt/>): E-REDES is the electricity distribution company operating in mainland Portugal, including Alentejo Central. It provides infrastructure access, manages smart metering systems, and enables collective self-consumption arrangements in accordance with national legislation.
- ADRAL – Alentejo Regional Development Agency (<https://www.adral.pt/>): A relevant enabling stakeholder for project development and articulation with regional development instruments, partnerships, and potential co-financing channels that may support REC implementation.

- Regional engineering and PV installation companies: A set of local and regional companies, including energy cooperatives and certified installers, will be involved in the dimensioning, procurement, installation, and maintenance of PV systems. These companies will also contribute to local capacity-building and job creation.

Public bodies

- Direção-Geral de Energia e Geologia (DGEG, <https://www.dgeg.gov.pt/>): DGEG is the Portuguese authority responsible for regulating and supervising the energy sector, including licensing, community energy schemes, and grid integration.
- Municipalities of Alentejo Central: The 14 municipal governments are essential stakeholders in the REC, providing logistical support, public buildings and rooftops, technical teams, and citizen engagement platforms.

4. Sizing of PV systems

The sizing of PV systems for the Alentejo Central Renewable Energy Community (REC) follows the methodological logic applied in JALON replication designs, while adapting the technical target to the Portuguese context and to the level of information available at the project design stage. In line with the JALON approach, PV is initially designed for self-consumption without storage, in order to reduce upfront investment and implementation complexity; storage can be incorporated in later stages once the REC is operational and load/production profiles are better characterized.

Three categories of PV systems are considered:

- Collective PV systems for residential prosumers
- Collective PV systems for local businesses and municipal/public services
- Individual or collective PV systems for industrial consumers

Two methodological pillars are applied consistently across the three segments. In line with the JALON methodology, the sizing logic is anchored in diffusion-of-innovation theory, which considers “early adopters” as a realistic initial target group for community-based innovations (13.5% of consumers)¹¹. Based on Portuguese national electricity consumption and PV production profiles for 2025¹², approximately 60% of annual electricity consumption occurs during sunshine hours, when PV is produced. The REC target is to cover 50% of that PV-hour consumption, corresponding to a self-sufficiency rate of 50% in solar hours. This translates into PV generation sized to supply ~30% of annual electricity consumption of the participating cohort. This choice is consistent with a “no-storage-first” design: it prioritizes high self-consumption and minimizes exported surpluses in the absence of batteries and detailed participant profiles. The conversion from annual energy (kWh/year) to PV capacity (kWp) uses the Alentejo Central productivity value of 1,613 kWh/kWp/year adopted in the project baseline.

4.1 Collective PV Systems for Residential Prosumers

Collective PV systems for residential prosumers will be prioritised over individual installations, as collective self-consumption enables economies of scale (shared engineering, procurement, installation and O&M), reduces unit costs, and supports a stronger sense of community participation.

For each municipality, the number of early-adopter households is estimated as 13.5% of domestic electricity consumers. The municipal residential consumption is converted into an average consumption per household, multiplied by the number of early adopters, and then scaled to 30% of annual consumption (PV-hour matching target). Required PV capacity is finally obtained by dividing the targeted annual PV energy by 1,613 kWh/kWp/year.

The resulting sizing (Table 2) shows substantial heterogeneity across the territory, reflecting the strong demographic differences between municipalities. The largest PV requirement occurs in Évora (2.17 MWp), followed by Montemor-o-Novo (649.8 kWp), while smaller municipalities

¹¹ Rogers, E. M. (1962). Diffusion of innovations. Free Press of Glencoe

¹² REN. “Eletricidade. Balanço diário” [ONLINE] Accessed Jan, 6 2026. Available: <https://datahub.ren.pt/pt/eletricidade/balanco-diario/>

such as Mourão (102.8 kWp) show comparatively modest initial capacity needs. At regional level, the early-adopter cohort amounts to 12,068 households, corresponding to an estimated PV capacity of 6.28 MWp to offset 30% of the demand of these participants.

In the first implementation stage, the REC will not aim to deploy the full theoretical early-adopter capacity simultaneously across all municipalities but will prioritise a portfolio of seven municipalities (50% of the municipalities) to concentrate engagement resources, validate governance and operational procedures, and deliver demonstrator PV self-consumption projects that are scalable and replicable. The selected municipalities are Évora, Montemor-o-Novo, Estremoz, Reguengos de Monsaraz, Vendas Novas, Arraiolos, and Alandroal.

This selection combines (i) a regional anchor municipality with strong institutional capacity and demonstrator value (Évora), (ii) mid-sized municipalities where deployment can achieve meaningful scale while remaining operationally manageable (Montemor-o-Novo, Estremoz, Reguengos de Monsaraz, Vendas Novas), and (iii) smaller municipalities that ensure territorial cohesion and demonstrate the added value of a regional REC for communities that would face higher barriers to develop local RECs independently (Arraiolos and Alandroal). The PV capacity requirement for the early-adopter cohort in these municipalities is 4,709.2 kWp affecting 8,841 households. The same methodology will be progressively extended to the remaining municipalities in subsequent stages.

Table 2: Estimated number of early adopter households and required PV capacity for each municipality. *Selected municipalities for stage 1.

Municipality	Number of early adopter residential consumers	Required PV Capacity (kWp)
Alandroal*	487	230.8
Arraiolos*	575	302.7
Borba	493	268.0
Estremoz*	1047	493.3
Évora*	3824	2173.2
Montemor-o-Novo*	1223	649.8
Mora	435	172.8
Mourão	227	102.8
Portel	513	243.9
Redondo	534	258.3
Reguengos de Monsaraz*	847	435.4
Vendas Novas*	838	424.0
Viana do Alentejo	447	227.6
Vila Viçosa	578	294.4
Total	12068	6277.0

4.2 Collective PV Systems for Local Businesses and Municipal Services

Collective self-consumption PV systems are also planned for local businesses, local commerce, and municipal services, as these actors are essential for territorial cohesion, local economic resilience, and the credibility of the REC. In addition to increasing the local impact of renewable

generation, the involvement of municipalities and public buildings strengthens trust and accelerates engagement by providing visible anchor projects.

The sizing approach for this segment uses the same proxy logic used for residential consumers: PV systems are dimensioned so that annual PV generation is equivalent to 30% of the annual electricity demand of the participating entities. For each municipality, the annual electricity demand associated with local businesses and services was approximated through the non-residential electricity consumption, while the municipal and public-service component was approximated through the electricity demand for lighting of public buildings^{1,2}. To operationalise the early adoption dynamic, the participation target was applied to the number of consumers categorized with non-residential and illumination of public buildings^{1,2}: an early adopter share of 13.5% was assumed for both the non-residential segment and the public-service segment, consistent with diffusion-of-innovation theory¹⁰. The annual energy targets (kWh/year) computed using 30% of the average energy demand per consumer and the number of early-adopter consumers of each category were then converted into required PV capacity (kWp) using the PV productivity value adopted for Alentejo Central (1,613 kWh/kWp/year).

The results are summarised in Table 3. The estimates highlight strong territorial heterogeneity, driven primarily by differences in municipal population and activity levels. As expected, Évora concentrates the highest required capacity, while smaller municipalities present comparatively lower requirements. For stage 1 implementation, and to ensure consistency with the territorial prioritisation adopted for the residential segment, collective PV systems for local businesses and municipal services will be developed in the same seven municipalities selected: Évora, Montemor-o-Novo, Estremoz, Reguengos de Monsaraz, Vendas Novas, Arraiolos, and Alandroal. Based on Table 3, the corresponding required PV capacity for the early-adopter cohort in these municipalities totals 4,302.32 kWp. In later stages, the same methodology will be replicated to the remaining municipalities as participation increases and additional demand aggregation becomes feasible.

Table 3: Estimated early adopters in the categories of non-residential and lighting of public buildings energy demand and required PV capacity for each municipality. *Selected municipalities for stage 1.

Municipality	Number of non-residential early adopters	Number of early adopter consumers in the category of illumination of public buildings	Required PV Capacity (kWp)
Alandroal*	31	15	156.44
Arraiolos*	44	7	147.26
Borba	48	11	134.27
Estremoz*	137	27	477.70
Évora*	430	65	2410.40
Montemor-o-Novo*	124	35	533.77
Mora	27	14	140.71
Mourão	16	12	87.19
Portel	27	8	104.05
Redondo	35	11	201.77

Municipality	Number of non-residential early adopters	Number of early adopter consumers in the category of illumination of public buildings	Required PV Capacity (kWp)
Reguengos de Monsaraz*	75	23	316.70
Vendas Novas*	70	13	260.05
Viana do Alentejo	29	9	110.76
Vila Viçosa	55	14	209.65
Total	1148	264	5290.72

4.3 Individual/Collective PV Systems for Industries

In addition to residential prosumers and service-sector participants, the Alentejo Central REC will promote PV self-consumption systems for industrial consumers, given the relevance of industrial electricity demand in the region and the potential for large and stable load profiles to support both decarbonisation and the financial robustness of the REC. Industrial participation is also strategically important to demonstrate that the REC model can integrate a diversity of local actors and contribute to competitiveness and resilience in rural territories.

The sizing approach for the industrial segment follows the same demand-matching logic applied in the previous subsections: PV capacity is dimensioned so that annual PV generation is equivalent to 30% of the annual electricity demand of the participating industrial cohort. At the project design stage, detailed consumption data for each individual industrial facility are not yet available. Therefore, a municipality-level proxy was adopted using sectoral electricity consumption indicators, applying the early-adoption dynamic to the number of industry electricity consumers. The annual energy targets (kWh/year) computed using 30% of the average energy demand per consumer and the number of early-adopter consumers in the industry category were then converted into required PV capacity (kWp) using the PV productivity value adopted for Alentejo Central (1,613 kWh/kWp/year).

The resulting estimates are presented in Table 4. They highlight substantial territorial heterogeneity, reflecting differences in industrial activity. The required PV capacity ranges from comparatively small values in municipalities with lower industrial demand to very large values where industrial consumption is concentrated.

Table 4: Estimated early adopter industrial energy demand and required PV capacity for each municipality. *Selected municipalities for stage 1.

Municipality	Early adopter consumers in the industry category (kWh)	Required PV Capacity (kWp)
Alandroal*	9	58.93
Arraiolos*	11	99.22
Borba	11	173.96
Estremoz*	18	170.04
Évora*	70	2599.78
Montemor-o-Novo*	29	438.29

Municipality	Early adopter consumers in the industry category (kWh)	Required PV Capacity (kWp)
Mora	4	114.65
Mourão	4	24.63
Portel	9	2580.28
Redondo	11	88.19
Reguengos de Monsaraz*	15	251.30
Vendas Novas*	16	545.48
Viana do Alentejo	8	72.30
Vila Viçosa	15	351.13
Total	230	7568.20

For stage 1 implementation, and to maintain alignment with the territorial prioritisation adopted for the residential segment and for local businesses/municipal services, the industrial PV self-consumption portfolio will also be initiated in the same seven municipalities selected for Phase 1: Évora, Montemor-o-Novo, Estremoz, Reguengos de Monsaraz, Vendas Novas, Arraiolos, and Alandroal. Based on Table 4, the corresponding required PV capacity for the early-adopter industrial cohort in these municipalities totals 4,163.05 kWp. The remaining municipalities will be progressively incorporated in subsequent stages as engagement, technical readiness, and financing capacity expand.

4.4 Stage 1 total installed PV

For the purposes of implementation planning and financial modelling, stage 1 requires translating the municipality-level PV capacity targets (Tables 2–4) into a discrete portfolio of PV projects that can be procured, permitted, financed, and operated. In this project design, a PV system is defined as a single installation associated with a specific site and point of connection (i.e., one engineering project with a metering and grid-connection configuration). To ensure modularity, facilitate phased deployment, and limit the complexity of early implementation, the PV capacity in each municipality and category is structured into standardised capacity blocks of 100 kWp, with an additional “balance” system where needed to match the remaining capacity. This approach preserves the demand-matching logic used for sizing while producing an actionable and finance-ready project pipeline.

Applying this modularisation to the seven municipalities selected for stage 1 (Évora, Montemor-o-Novo, Estremoz, Reguengos de Monsaraz, Vendas Novas, Arraiolos and Alandroal) results in a portfolio as shown in Table 5.

These values provide the reference basis for the subsequent financial model, including CAPEX estimation, financing structure, revenue projections, and the phased business plan of the REC with a total of 142 PV installations with a 13,174.57 kWp and impacting 8,841 residential consumers.

Table 5: Summary of PV self-consumption systems for stage 1 of Alentejo Central REC.

Type of PV system	Number of systems	Total power (kWp)
Collective for residential	51	4709.20
Collective for local shops and municipalities	47	4302.32
Individual or collective for industries	44	4163.05

5. Financial model

Energy communities have demonstrated that it is possible to combine renewable energy production with social and economic benefits for the local population. In practice, REC business models vary according to local objectives and enabling conditions, but they typically aim to (i) mobilise investment for local renewable generation, (ii) deliver lower and more stable energy costs for members, and (iii) reinvest value locally through services, employment, and community programmes. For the Alentejo Central REC, the financial model is therefore designed to be implementation-oriented and socially aligned: it defines the investment required to deploy the project, proposes realistic funding channels, and structures revenues and costs in a way that sustains operations without making profit maximisation the primary objective.

5.1 Business model options considered

The Alentejo Central REC design considers the following business-model options, which can be combined and adjusted during the seeding phase:

Option A — Service-based shared self-consumption model (REC as an operator). The REC acts as a coordinating operator for shared self-consumption (collective and/or individual self-consumption schemes aggregated under the REC). Members benefit from locally produced electricity and reduced exposure to retail price volatility. Cost recovery is structured through a transparent fee system combining:

- a one-time membership/entrance fee to formalise participation and support onboarding;
- an energy fee (€/kWh) associated with locally supplied electricity and REC services;
- an annual contract/administrative fee reflecting metering, billing, management, and compliance functions.

This model is well aligned with a regional REC because it supports standardised processes, replication across municipalities, and the integration of different actor types (households, services, municipalities, industry) under a coherent operational framework.

Option B — Cooperative/solidarity value model (benefit reinvestment and cross-municipal cohesion). Regardless of legal form, the REC can adopt a cooperative-type value allocation logic, meaning that any operational surplus is not treated as profit maximisation but as a mechanism to:

- reinvest in REC expansion (new PV projects, storage, energy efficiency);
- fund targeted social measures to address energy vulnerability (e.g., reduced fees for vulnerable households, support via local IPSS);
- finance community services that reinforce territorial cohesion (training, engagement, monitoring, local technical capacity).

This logic is particularly relevant in low-density territories, where the REC's legitimacy depends on visible local value creation and fairness of benefit distribution.

Option C — Anchor-load integration model (industrial/municipal anchors supporting viability). A regional REC can explicitly include "anchor" members (e.g., industries and municipal services with stable demand profiles) to strengthen the financial base and reduce variability risks. In this model, the REC remains inclusive and citizen-led, but gains operational robustness through

demand aggregation and predictable consumption patterns. The presence of anchors can enable more favourable conditions for the whole membership base (e.g., lower fees for households) while maintaining compliance with REC principles (open participation, community benefit orientation).

These options are not mutually exclusive. The baseline design in this document adopts Option A as the operational core, complemented by Option B to ensure social purpose and reinvestment, and Option C to enhance stability and scalability at regional level. The detailed pricing policy (membership fees, €/kWh fee, contract fees) is defined in the Business Plan section based on affordability constraints, expected member savings, and debt-service requirements when repayable financing is used.

5.2 Investment requirements

Stage 1 is implemented through three PV segments across the seven selected municipalities (Alandroal, Arraiolos, Estremoz, Évora, Montemor-o-Novo, Reguengos de Monsaraz and Vendas Novas): (i) collective PV for residential consumers, (ii) collective PV for local shops and municipal services, and (iii) individual or collective PV for industries. To support procurement and phased delivery, the PV capacity in each municipality and segment is organised into standardised 100 kWp installations, complemented where necessary by a smaller “balance” installation to reach the required capacity.

Under the CAPEX assumptions adopted for stage 1 and considering cost per kWp of €0,9840 for a 50kWp system and of €0,7995 for a 100kWp system including VAT obtained from previous consultations by the University of Évora a linear PV system cost is assumed, and the PV investment totals €10,670,320.22, distributed as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Summary of PV capacity and CAPEX for stage 1 of Alentejo Central REC.

PV segment	Installed capacity (kWp)	Total CAPEX (€)
Collective PV for residential consumption	4,709.20	3,807,788.08
Collective PV for local shops & municipal services	4,302.32	3,490,045.05
Individual/collective PV for industries	4,163.05	3,372,487.09
Total	13,174.57	10,670,320.22

In addition to PV CAPEX, the model includes enabling resources required to launch the REC and execute Phase 1 implementation activities (seeding the idea phase), as shown in Table 7. These enabling costs are estimated at €67,350 per year, corresponding to €134,700 over the year before the PV installation and the year of PV installation start, and are treated as a distinct funding need associated with the initial deployment phase.

Table 7: seeding the idea phase annual costs.

Seeding the idea phase	Annual cost (€)
Personnel (2)	56,000
Transport	7,200
Office equipment	1,000
Telephone	150
Communication materials	2,000
Other communication tools (web, social media, etc)	1,000
Total	67,350

5.3 Financing approach and public funding relevance

The financial structure combines (i) non-repayable public support to reduce affordability pressure on members and (ii) repayable capital to finance the remaining share of PV CAPEX. This is consistent with the nature of a REC as a public-interest initiative: the objective is not to maximise returns, but to ensure that investment recovery is feasible while maintaining equitable access and tangible bill savings for members.

Public financing can be mobilised through several mechanisms that are relevant to energy communities and local administrations. Examples of instruments that are aligned with REC development and/or municipal PV deployment include:

- [The European Energy Communities Facility](#), which provides a one-time grant of €45,000 to support emerging energy communities in developing robust business plans for renewable energy projects (including training and ongoing guidance), with eligibility linked to EU definitions of energy communities and a formal application process.
- Regional programmes under Portugal 2030 that support renewable energy and climate adaptation investment, including a call for “[Promotion of Self-Consumption and Renewable Energy Communities](#)” offering a maximum co-financing rate of 85% as well as calls focused on territorial instruments and local administration energy efficiency and decarbonisation measures that may include PV installation on public buildings (e.g., [Material Actions for Climate Change Adaptation – ITI Water and Landscape Ecosystems – Algarve and Alentejo](#), [Energy Efficiency in Local Administration – ITI CIM](#)).
- National mechanisms such as compensation schemes for municipalities related to renewable generation or self-consumption installations, which can create complementary municipal incentives and improve local feasibility conditions ([Support for Compensation to Municipalities for the Installation of Power Generation Centers](#)).

In the stage 1 model, public funding plays two distinct roles: Enabling funding, used to cover the initial two-year deployment and coordination effort (the “seeding the idea phase” cost); CAPEX co-financing, used to reduce the repayable burden of PV investment and thereby protect member affordability.

5.4 Base financing mix and debt assumptions

For implementation planning, the model adopts a simple and replicable base financing mix for PV CAPEX assuming the 85% non-repayable grant provided by the regional programme for Alentejo under Portugal 2030 (ALT 2030):

- Public funding (grant): 85% of PV CAPEX amounting to €9,069,772.19
- Repayable financing (bank or crowdlending): 15% of PV CAPEX amounting to €1,600,548.03

The same study was carried out for a more conservative percentage of financing from non-repayable public funds (60%) and is presented in an annex of this document.

Membership entrance fees are modelled as a separate liquidity stream linked to participation (not as a primary CAPEX financing mechanism). The entrance-fee assumptions used are €50 per household, €100 per commercial/municipal participant and €100 per industrial participant, which yields €568,450 when the stage 1 cohort is fully enrolled.

The repayable portion is modelled with standard amortising debt logic using nominal interest rate of 4%, a tenor of 10 years and annual debt service payments.

This debt module is integrated into the REC cash flow alongside operational revenues (fees and energy-related charges) and operating expenditures. The resulting cash-flow outputs are presented in the next section and are used to confirm that the REC can be implemented with financial stability while maintaining the REC's social purpose and affordability objectives.

6. Business plan

The purpose of this business plan is not to maximise financial profit, but to ensure the long-term economic sustainability of the community while delivering the core objectives associated with Renewable Energy Communities under the EU framework: enabling citizen participation in the energy transition, reducing energy costs and energy vulnerability, strengthening territorial cohesion, and keeping value creation local through collective ownership and reinvestment. In this context, financial performance indicators are used as feasibility and resilience checks rather than as targets in themselves.

6.1. Phase 1: Seeding the idea phase

This phase comprises year 0 and 1 of the project being year 1 when the REC is constituted and the first installations are built and the first members enter the community. For the seeding the idea phase non-repayable public funding was considered to cover all the expenses (€134,700.00) over the two years.

6.2. Phases 2 and 3: REC creation and operation phase

The business plan for the REC operation phase assumes that 85% of the total CAPEX is obtained from non-repayable public funding (€9,069,772.19) with 15% being obtained from loan or crowdlending (€1,600,548). The cost of installing the PV and loan/crowdlending funds are distributed from year 1 to year 3 assuming 30% of the cost and funds in years 1 and 3 and 40% in year 2. For each tranche of the loans the annual instalment for a period of 10 years was computed using a 4% nominal interest rate. Table 8 presents the funding balance and the capex

costs throughout the 20 year life of the project without the values gained and paid related to public funding.

Table 8: 20 year balance of funding and PV CAPEX.

Year	Funding balance (€)	PV CAPEX (€)
1	480 164.41	- 480 164.41
2	581 019.29	- 640 219.21
3	342 031.25	- 480 164.41
4	- 197 333.08	-
5	- 197 333.08	-
6	- 197 333.08	-
7	- 197 333.08	-
8	- 197 333.08	-
9	- 197 333.08	-
10	- 197 333.08	-
11	- 197 333.08	-
12	- 138 133.15	-
13	- 59 199.92	-
14	-	-
15	-	-
16	-	-
17	-	-
18	-	-
19	-	-
20	-	-

The revenue of the REC comes from the Membership fees paid by members at the time they enter the REC, the electricity fees paid by the members proportional to the energy consumed and the contract fees paid annually by each member. The REC’s electricity cost was defined with a higher value in the first 10 years of a REC member as a way to help pay the loan instalments. Similar to the funding and CAPEX it was assumed that 30% of the early-adopter members entered the REC in years 1 and 3 and 40% in year 2.

Table 9: REC fees from the members.

Member type	Membership fee (€/member)	Electricity cost first 10 years (€/kWh)	Electricity cost after year 10 (€/kWh)	Contract fee (€/member/year)
Residential	50.00	0.06	0.046	5
Commercial and municipal	100.00	0.06	0.046	15
Industry	100.00	0.06	0.046	20

As for the annual expenses of the REC the operation and maintenance cost was computed considering a cost of €5,000.00 per MWp installed per year, costs with personnel were assumed €56,000.00 and with transportation €7,200.00 per year. There are also administrative and management expenses considered 4% of the REC’s revenue each year. The cost related to the network access rate is subtracted to the revenue obtained from electricity sales considering a rate of 0,04505€/kWh for households, commerce and municipalities and of 0,021033€/kWh for industries¹³. With these assumptions we obtain the operational balance of the REC shown in Table 10.

Table 10: 20-year balance of revenues from the REC’s members and annual expenses.

Year	Membership fees (€)	REC annual revenue (€)	REC annual expenses (€)
1	170 535.00	162 892.58	- 89 477.55
2	227 380.00	380 082.68	- 124 514.29
3	170 535.00	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
4	-	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
5	-	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
6	-	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
7	-	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
8	-	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
9	-	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
10	-	542 975.26	- 150 791.84
11	-	453 722.85	- 147 221.74
12	-	334 719.63	- 142 461.61
13	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52
14	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52
15	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52
16	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52
17	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52
18	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52
19	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52
20	-	245 467.21	- 138 891.52

Table 11 shows the unlevered (project, without financing) and levered (after financing) cashflow and accumulated cashflow. The project is economically viable under the stated assumptions. In the unlevered case (project cash flow, excluding financing), the accumulated cash flow turns positive in Year 4, meaning the project reaches a simple payback of roughly 4 years and has an IRR of 53.46%. In the levered case (including debt flows), the accumulated cash flow is positive from Year 1 and grows continuously although at different rates due to the changes in electricity tariffs and the amortization

¹³ ERSE (2026). Quadros de Tarifas Energia Eléctrica vigentes a partir de 01 de janeiro de 2026. Accessed on Jan. 29, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://www.erse.pt/media/wfziq5t5/s_tarifas_net.xlsx

of debt. The accumulated balance remains positive throughout the 20-year horizon, ending at €3.41M.

Table 11: Unlevered and Levered 20 year balance of the REC.

Year	Unlevered		Levered	
	Cash Flow (€)	Accumulated Cash Flow (€)	Cash Flow (€)	Accumulated Cash Flow (€)
1	- 236 214.38	- 236 214.38	243 950.03	243 950.03
2	- 157 270.82	- 393 485.20	423 748.47	667 698.50
3	82 554.01	- 310 931.19	424 585.27	1 092 283.76
4	392 183.42	81 252.23	194 850.34	1 287 134.11
5	392 183.42	473 435.65	194 850.34	1 481 984.45
6	392 183.42	865 619.07	194 850.34	1 676 834.79
7	392 183.42	1 257 802.49	194 850.34	1 871 685.13
8	392 183.42	1 649 985.91	194 850.34	2 066 535.47
9	392 183.42	2 042 169.33	194 850.34	2 261 385.82
10	392 183.42	2 434 352.75	194 850.34	2 456 236.16
11	306 501.10	2 740 853.86	109 168.02	2 565 404.18
12	192 258.01	2 933 111.87	54 124.86	2 619 529.04
13	106 575.69	3 039 687.56	47 375.77	2 666 904.81
14	106 575.69	3 146 263.26	106 575.69	2 773 480.51
15	106 575.69	3 252 838.95	106 575.69	2 880 056.20
16	106 575.69	3 359 414.65	106 575.69	2 986 631.89
17	106 575.69	3 465 990.34	106 575.69	3 093 207.59
18	106 575.69	3 572 566.03	106 575.69	3 199 783.28
19	106 575.69	3 679 141.73	106 575.69	3 306 358.98
20	106 575.69	3 785 717.42	106 575.69	3 412 934.67

Table 12 presents the perspective of a residential REC member that enters the REC in year 1. This balance assumes the average savings considering the average residential energy consumption per consumer for the 7 municipalities of stage 1 and the electricity price paid to the electricity supplier of 0.1348€/kWh¹⁴. These values show a return of the investment from the start (year 1) and a gain of €1,174.02 after 20 years.

¹⁴ ERSE (2026). Simulador de eletricidade. Accessed on Jan. 29, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://simuladorprecos.erse.pt/eletricidade/>

Table 12: 20 year balance for a REC residential member.

Year	Cash Flow (€)	Accumulated Cash Flow (€)
1	5.54	5.54
2	55.54	61.07
3	55.54	116.61
4	55.54	172.14
5	55.54	227.68
6	55.54	283.22
7	55.54	338.75
8	55.54	394.29
9	55.54	449.82
10	55.54	505.36
11	66.87	572.23
12	66.87	639.09
13	66.87	705.96
14	66.87	772.83
15	66.87	839.69
16	66.87	906.56
17	66.87	973.42
18	66.87	1 040.29
19	66.87	1 107.16
20	66.87	1 174.02

7. Legal aspects

The incorporation of a legal entity in Portugal requires registration in the Register of Legal Entities, which grants legal personality and allows for its legal and tax identification. Each type of entity has its own rules of incorporation, required documentation, and associated costs.

1. Association

Associations are non-profit entities formed by a group of individuals united by common interests. To incorporate an association, it is necessary to draft bylaws, which define its objectives, governance structure, and governing bodies. Registration in the REC can be requested by any individual or legal person at the Civil, Land and Commercial Registries or through the IRN's online service. The estimated cost is €300. Whenever new members join, this must be recorded in the minutes and communicated for updating the records.

2. Commercial Company

Commercial companies aim to carry out economic activities for profit. Their incorporation requires the execution of a company agreement (articles of association), which may take different legal forms (public limited company, private limited company, general partnership, etc.). This contract sets out shareholdings (quotas or shares), the rights and obligations of shareholders, and the company's governance model. Registration in the REC is mandatory, and the estimated cost is €360. Any changes, such as the entry of new shareholders, require amendments to the company agreement, formalized by public deed or authenticated private document, and must be updated in the registry.

3. Cooperative

Cooperatives are independent, non-profit entities operating based on collaboration and mutual assistance among members, aiming to meet economic, social, or cultural needs. Incorporation requires the participation of at least three individuals and the drafting of bylaws that enshrine cooperative principles and rules of operation. In addition, registration in the Central Register of Beneficial Owners (RCBE) is mandatory. The cost of registration is €360. New members must be approved in the general assembly and recorded in the cooperative's official records, with subsequent communication to the REC if the change affects its structure.

4. Foundation

Foundations are non-profit entities created by one or more individuals (founders) who allocate assets to a social, cultural, or public-interest purpose. Incorporation requires the drafting of foundation bylaws and the execution of a founding act (public deed or will, when applicable). Registration in the REC can be requested by the founders or by legal representatives, such as attorneys, lawyers, or notaries. The estimated cost is €300. The entry of new members into the foundation's governing bodies or amendments to its bylaws must be formalized and communicated to the supervisory authority, namely the Secretariat-General of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers and registered accordingly.

In all cases, registration in the REC is an essential condition for the legal recognition of the entity and must be updated whenever structural changes occur, including the admission of new shareholders, members, cooperators, or governing body representatives.

While this project design identifies several viable legal pathways for the constitution of the REC in Portugal the final selection of the legal entity will remain open to deliberation during the initial 'Seeding and Mobilisation' phase. This approach ensures that the chosen structure fully aligns with the participatory governance and strategic vision co-developed by the core promotional group and regional stakeholders. It is important to note that each legal form carries specific administrative requirements and associated registration costs. Although these initial registration fees have not been explicitly accounted for in the current business plan, they will be formally integrated into the detailed operational budget once the legal constitution is finalized, ensuring the REC's total financial coherence from its inception.

8. Methodology for engagement

The methodology for generating engagement in Alentejo Central and raising awareness among citizens, associations, local councils, small businesses, and other key stakeholders will be based on the tools, processes, and lessons developed within the JALON project. In particular, it builds on the participatory dynamics tested during the implementation of the regional REC in Calatayud, adapting them to the Portuguese legal, cultural, and territorial context.

Given the region's demographic structure and spatial dispersion, the engagement strategy will prioritise local presence, trust-building, and inclusive participation across the 14 municipalities of Alentejo Central. The process will be coordinated by CIMAC and UEVORA, in collaboration with municipal technicians, local associations, and a dedicated field team.

Key elements of the methodology include:

- Establishment of a regional promotional group, composed of institutional partners, technicians, and volunteer stakeholders, to guide the vision, language, and materials used during the engagement process;
- Direct collaboration with municipalities and parish councils, especially mayors and local officials, to secure community trust and logistical support for meetings and workshops;
- Organisation of public assemblies and co-design workshops in each municipality, aimed at informing citizens, gathering feedback, and co-developing aspects of the REC, such as governance rules, benefit-sharing mechanisms, and membership models;
- Targeted outreach to local associations, SMEs, farmers, and public institutions, using tailored communication strategies that speak to the specific concerns and motivations of each group;
- Field deployment of a trained facilitation team, who will manage the implementation of the participatory plan on the ground providing technical clarifications, moderating discussions, and ensuring follow-up actions;
- Use of adapted JALON engagement tools, including templates for invitations, facilitation guides, participation tracking forms, and legal/institutional information materials translated into Portuguese and contextualised for Alentejo Central;
- Ensuring inclusiveness, with specific actions directed at low-income households, elderly residents, and those in remote or underserved areas, using channels such as local media, municipal newsletters, and community centres.

The engagement methodology aims not only to inform but to empower local actors, ensuring that the REC emerges from within the community and reflects the region's real needs, values, and capacities. The process will be iterative and adaptive, with room for feedback loops, informal consultations, and evolving forms of participation as the REC design matures.

9. Conclusions

In conclusion, the Regional Energy Community Project Design for Alentejo Central provides a comprehensive and actionable blueprint for a transition toward a decentralized, citizen-led energy model. By adapting the established JALON methodology to the unique socio-economic and territorial characteristics of the Alentejo region, the project seeks to address critical structural challenges such as rural depopulation, energy poverty, and economic marginalization.

The design is structured across three implementation phases: Mobilization, Project Development, and Operation, to ensure technical viability and social inclusivity. Key highlights of the proposed design include:

- **Integrated Territorial Strategy:** Leveraging the coordination of CIMAC and the expertise of the University of Évora to foster cooperation across 14 municipalities. The REC acts as a strategic instrument to combat the structural fragilities of Beira Baixa, namely depopulation and energy poverty. By decentralizing energy production and lowering costs for 8,841 residential consumers, the community strengthens the socio-economic fabric of low-density municipalities.
- **Technically Sized for Impact:** A phased deployment of photovoltaic systems focused on early adopters to cover approximately 30% of the annual electricity consumption of participating members with stage 1 portfolio of 142 PV systems with a total capacity of 13,174.57 kWp.
- **Sustainable Financial Model:** A mix of public funding (85%) and repayable financing (15%) designed to ensure the project remains economically viable while maintaining affordable energy prices for residents, businesses, and local industries. The business model shows an unlevered payback period of 4 years and a 20-year levered accumulated balance of €3.41M, the project generates sufficient surplus to ensure long-term maintenance while protecting member affordability.
- **Strong Social Foundation:** A bottom-up approach that prioritizes transparency, local empowerment, and a legal structure to ensure benefits are redistributed equitably across the community.

Ultimately, this project serves as more than an infrastructure plan, it is a catalyst for territorial regeneration and a replicable model for other low-density rural territories across Europe. By successfully aligning technical solutions with local needs, Alentejo Central is poised to become a pioneer in community-driven climate resilience and energy democracy.

10. Annex - REC Business plan with 60% public funding

This annex presents the business plan for the REC creation and operation phases assuming a percentage of financing from public funding of 60% instead of the previously stated 85%. This is a more conservative and common value found for public financing and so this study might be more relevant depending on the financing options available.

The business plan for the REC operation phase assumes that 60% of the total CAPEX is obtained from non-repayable public funding (€6,402,192.13) with 40% being obtained from loan or crowdlending (€4,268,128.09). The cost of installing the PV and loan/crowdlending funds are distributed from year 1 to year 3 assuming 30% of the cost and funds in years 1 and 3 and 40% in year 2. For each tranche of the loans the annual instalment for a period of 10 years was computed using a 4% nominal interest rate. Table 13 presents the funding balance and the capex costs throughout the 20 year life of the project without the values gained and paid related to public funding.

Table 13: 20 year balance of funding and PV CAPEX.

Year	Funding balance (€)	PV CAPEX (€)
1	1 280 438.43	- 1 280 438.43
2	1 549 384.77	- 1 707 251.23
3	912 083.35	- 1 280 438.43
4	- 526 221.54	-
5	- 526 221.54	-
6	- 526 221.54	-
7	- 526 221.54	-
8	- 526 221.54	-
9	- 526 221.54	-
10	- 526 221.54	-
11	- 526 221.54	-
12	- 368 355.08	-
13	- 157 866.46	-
14	-	-
15	-	-
16	-	-
17	-	-
18	-	-
19	-	-
20	-	-

The revenue of the REC comes from the Membership fees paid by members at the time they enter the REC, the electricity fees paid by the members proportional to the energy consumed and the contract fees paid annually by each member. The REC's electricity cost was defined with a higher value in the first 10 years of a REC member as a way to help pay the loan instalments.

Similar to the funding and CAPEX it was assumed that 30% of the early-adopter members entered the REC in years 1 and 3 and 40% in year 2.

Table 14: REC fees from the members.

Member type	Membership fee (€/member)	Electricity cost first 10 years (€/kWh)	Electricity cost after year 10 (€/kWh)	Contract fee (€/member/year)
Residential	50.00	0.07	0.046	5
Commercial and municipal	100.00	0.07	0.046	15
Industry	100.00	0.07	0.046	20

As for the annual expenses of the REC the operation and maintenance cost was computed considering a cost of €5,00.00 per MWp installed per year, costs with personnel were assumed €56,000.00 and with transportation €7,200.00 per year. There are also administrative and management expenses considered 4% of the REC's revenue each year. The cost related to the network access rate is subtracted to the revenue obtained from electricity sales considering a rate of 0,04505€/kWh for households, commerce and municipalities and of 0,021033€/kWh for industries¹³. With these assumptions we obtain the operational balance of the REC shown in Table 15.

Table 15: 20 year balance of revenues from the REC's members and annual expenses.

Year	Membership fees (€)	REC annual revenue (€)	REC annual expenses (€)
1	170 535.00	226 644.30	- 92 027.62
2	227 380.00	528 836.71	- 130 464.45
3	170 535.00	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
4	-	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
5	-	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
6	-	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
7	-	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
8	-	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
9	-	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
10	-	755 481.01	- 159 292.07
11	-	602 476.87	-153 171.90
12	-	398 471.35	-145 011.68
13	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52
14	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52
15	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52
16	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52
17	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52
18	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52
19	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52
20	-	245 467.21	-138 891.52

Table 16 shows the unlevered (project, without financing) and levered (after financing) cashflow and accumulated cashflow. The project is economically viable under the stated assumptions, but its capacity to generate surplus is front-loaded and strongly driven by the pricing policy and the debt service profile. In the unlevered case (project cash flow, excluding financing), the accumulated cash flow turns positive in Year 8, meaning the project reaches a simple payback of roughly 8 years and has an IRR of 13.44%. After that, annual net operating surpluses remain positive but decline sharply from Year 11 onward, consistent with the step-down in the REC electricity price after the first 10 years of membership. In the levered case (including debt flows), the accumulated cash flow is positive from Year 1 and grows until Year 10, but then drops in Years 11–13 because the revenues decrease when the electricity tariff decreases and the debt service remains significant. Nevertheless, the accumulated balance remains positive throughout the 20-year horizon, ending at €2.16M.

Table 16: Unlevered and Levered 20 year balance of the REC.

Year	Unlevered		Levered	
	Cash Flow (€)	Accumulated Cash Flow (€)	Cash Flow (€)	Accumulated Cash Flow (€)
1	-975 286.74	-975 286.74	305 151.68	305 151.68
2	-1 081 498.98	-2 056 785.72	467 885.80	773 037.48
3	-513 714.49	-2 570 500.21	398 368.86	1 171 406.34
4	596 188.94	-1 974 311.27	69 967.40	1 241 373.73
5	596 188.94	-1 378 122.33	69 967.40	1 311 341.13
6	596 188.94	-781 933.39	69 967.40	1 381 308.53
7	596 188.94	-185 744.45	69 967.40	1 451 275.93
8	596 188.94	410 444.49	69 967.40	1 521 243.32
9	596 188.94	1 006 633.43	69 967.40	1 591 210.72
10	596 188.94	1 602 822.37	69 967.40	1 661 178.12
11	449 304.97	2 052 127.34	-76 916.58	1 584 261.54
12	253 459.67	2 305 587.00	-114 895.41	1 469 366.13
13	106 575.69	2 412 162.70	-51 290.77	1 418 075.36
14	106 575.69	2 518 738.39	106 575.69	1 524 651.06
15	106 575.69	2 625 314.09	106 575.69	1 631 226.75
16	106 575.69	2 731 889.78	106 575.69	1 737 802.44
17	106 575.69	2 838 465.48	106 575.69	1 844 378.14
18	106 575.69	2 945 041.17	106 575.69	1 950 953.83
19	106 575.69	3 051 616.86	106 575.69	2 057 529.53
20	106 575.69	3 158 192.56	106 575.69	2 164 105.22

Table 17 presents the perspective of a residential REC member that enters the REC in year 1. This balance assumes the average savings considering the average residential energy consumption per consumer for the 7 municipalities of stage 1 and the electricity price paid to

the electricity supplier of 0.1348€/kWh¹⁴. These values show a return of the investment in year 2 and a gain of €1,093.09 after 20 years.

Table 17: 20 year balance for a REC residential member.

Year	Cash Flow (€)	Accumulated Cash Flow (€)
1	-2.56	-2.56
2	47.44	44.89
3	47.44	92.33
4	47.44	139.77
5	47.44	187.21
6	47.44	234.66
7	47.44	282.10
8	47.44	329.54
9	47.44	376.99
10	47.44	424.43
11	66.87	491.30
12	66.87	558.16
13	66.87	625.03
14	66.87	691.90
15	66.87	758.76
16	66.87	825.63
17	66.87	892.49
18	66.87	959.36
19	66.87	1 026.23
20	66.87	1 093.09